

DRAPABILITY EVALUATION OF ADHESIVE-BONDED NCF BY MEANS OF LOW-FIDELITY SIMULATION

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Motivation

- Large scale production series for tailored non-crimp fabrics (NCF)
 - Layer bonding achieved by in-line feeding of adhesive binder
 - Adhesive web binder added in layered form
 - Omission of stitching process
- Need for drapability characterization for **holistic process optimization**
 - Draping mechanisms
 - Material characterization
 - Low-fidelity approaches required

Adhesive-bonded NCF

Thermoplastic grid to ensure integrity of layer

Backside of the UD-Layer without thermoplastic grid

Thermoplastic adhesive web between two layers

UD-Layer, Panex PX 35, 80g/m²

- **Forming mechanisms:**
 - Shearing and fibre slippage
 - Degree of slippage dependant on binder distribution
 - Rather high bending stiffness

Material characterization

Bias extension for shear stiffness

Cantilever test for bending stiffness

- Study of influence of:
 - Binder quantity
 - Consolidation pressure
 - stacking-sequence

Continuum Model FEM-Simulation

- Material data fed to FE-model
- Comparison between membrane, pre-integrated shell and experiment
- Comparison of draw-in behavior

Thank you for your attention!

Are there any questions?